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DECISION-MAKING OF FARM HOUSEHOLDS IN PREVENTING STUNTING IN LEMPAKE VILLAGE, NORTH SAMARINDA DISTRICT, SAMARINDA CITY

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Abstract

Stunting was a serious public health problem, especially in rural areas in Indonesia. Decision-making was the process of selecting an alternative course of action to achieve a predetermined goal or goal. Household decision-making had a significant impact on stunting prevention, especially in terms of food supply, health, and sanitation. The purpose of the study was to find out how decision-making was carried out and who was the most dominant in decision-making in farming households in the prevention of stunting in Kelurahan Lempake, Kecamatan Samarinda Utara. The study was conducted in Lempake Village, North Samarinda District, from November 2023 to February 2024, with data collected in the form of primary data through questionnaires and secondary data (library studies and related agencies). The sample was taken using random sampling purposive and the sample used was a group of prosperous farm women and a group of 34 respondents of night-time farmers. The methods of data analysis used were qualitative descriptive analysis and tabulation. The results of the study showed that the decision-making process began with the identification of stunting problems and the collection of information on stunting prevention. The husband and wife then jointly chose an alternative action, evaluated the alternative, and finally made a joint decision. This reflected a high awareness of the importance of having accurate information and adequate knowledge in quality decision-making. The decision-making of farming households in the prevention of stunting in Lempake Village showed that the wife's role in food-related decision-making was very dominant in farming households. However, the role of the husband was also involved, even to a lesser extent.

Keywords

Decision making, farming households, stunting.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the countries that is currently still facing several problems related to nutrition. One of the nutritional problems that is currently a major concern is the high number of stunted toddlers or what is commonly called stunting. Stunting is not an easy challenge for Indonesia in preparing to create a golden generation in 2045. Stunting can have a significant long-term impact on children's physical and cognitive growth and development, which in turn can hinder the potential of future generations. According to data from the Indonesian Ministry of Health, the prevalence of stunting in Indonesia is still quite high, namely at 21.6% in 2023, while the target to be achieved is 14% in 2024 [1].

Stunting is a condition where a child's growth is hampered due to a lack of nutrition over a long period of time. This can cause nutritional problems during infancy and difficulties in achieving normal growth in the future. Stunting is usually measured by comparing the child's height with WHO standards, with the stunting limit set if the z-score is $< -2SD$ to $-3SD$ [2]. The causes of stunting can come from direct factors such as poor nutrition during the pre-pregnancy period, pregnancy and breastfeeding. Other factors include short maternal height, early pregnancy, infections, hypertension, mental health problems, short birth spacing, IUGR, and premature birth. Indirect factors such as poor parenting patterns, food insecurity, inappropriate food allocation, home environmental conditions, lack of adequate activity stimulation, and low level of education of caregivers can also play a role in the occurrence of stunting [3].

Providing food is an important factor that plays a role in preventing stunting. This refers to the process of production, distribution and public access to sufficient, safe, nutritious and varied food. Aspects covered in food provision include agricultural production, distribution, economic availability, and meeting the nutritional needs of the community.

The availability of sufficient food, especially essential nutrients such as protein, iron and vitamins, is very important to prevent stunting. Apart from that, environmental cleanliness and health also play an important role. Clean water and poor sanitation can worsen the stunting problem because it can cause infections and other health problems. Therefore, providing adequate food and a clean and healthy environment is very important to prevent stunting [4].

Providing diverse, nutritious, balanced and safe food is the key to supporting community health and welfare. Diverse, nutritious, balanced and safe food is often also called B2SA food. Diverse food means that it includes the availability of various types of food from various sources, where the more diverse the more complete the nutritional content. Nutritious means it contains macro-nutrients (carbohydrates, protein, fat) & micro-nutrients (vitamins and minerals). Balanced means the amount must be in accordance with the needs of age, gender, activity, ideal weight, food group and meal times. Safe means free from chemical, physical and biological hazards [5].

East Kalimantan Province has a high stunting prevalence rate, especially in toddlers aged 0-59 months. The prevalence of stunting in 2023 according to Indonesian Health Survey data is 22.9% with a stunting reduction achievement target of 12.83%. The prevalence of stunting in East Kalimantan in 2022 varies in each region, ranging from 14.8 – 21.7%.

According to data from the Samarinda City Health Service, in 2022 there are 4 sub-districts in North Samarinda District that have stunted toddlers, namely: Bengkuring (19.8%), Sempaja (15.2%), Sungai Siring (3.9%) and Lempake (13.9%), the data shows that North Samarinda District is one of the areas that needs to be followed up regarding stunting, starting from prevention to stunting treatment.

Lempake Village, which is located in North Samarinda, relies on sectors such as forestry, mining, trade, plantations and livestock in its economy. Even though it has good physical and non-physical potential, such as a strong agricultural sector and community institutions, health problems

such as stunting show that aspects of welfare still need to be improved. As an agricultural area, Lempake Village has the Suluh Manuntung Agricultural Extension Center (BPP) which provides counseling to farmers. Data from the 2023 Agricultural Extension Management Information System (SIMLUHTAN) shows that there are 39 Farmer Groups and 16 Farmer Women's Groups. The two groups that were the focus of the research were the Sedap Malam Farmer Group and the Makmur Farmer Women's Group, because both were active and had members who had children.

Actions to prevent stunting in the household begin with a decision-making process. The act of choosing, buying or consuming food in the family begins with a decision-making process. Before looking at stunting prevention patterns, you need to know more about who plays a role in the decision-making process. Decision making in preventing stunting is influenced, among other things, by food availability and socio-cultural factors which include food culture, eating patterns, distribution of food in the family, family size, personal factors, nutritional knowledge, preferences and health status [6].

The research objective is to identify the decision-making process in farmer households in preventing stunting; and to find out who is most dominant in decision making in farmer households in preventing stunting in Lempake Village, North Samarinda District.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Place and Time

This research was carried out in Lempake Village, North Samarinda District from November 2023 to February 2024.

2.2. Method of collecting data

The data taken consisted of (1) primary data obtained by observing in the field and conducting direct interviews with respondents using a list of questions (questionnaire) which was prepared according to the problem and objectives of this research; and (2) secondary data obtained through various sources such as data regarding stunting through the Central Statistics Agency, Indonesian Health Survey, Samarinda City Health Service and Posyandu Bougainville, as well as data regarding Women's Farmers' Groups and Farmers' Groups obtained through the Agricultural Extension Center.

2.3. Sampling Method

The population in this study consisted of 39 farmer groups and women farmer groups in Lempake Village. The technique for determining respondents in this research is the non-probability sampling method, namely purposive sampling.

The criteria for respondents in this study were husband and/or wife farmers, domiciled in Lempake Village, and members of an active farmer group. The selection of active farmer group members is seen from 2 farmer groups in RT.41, namely the Makmur Women's Farmer Group and the Sedap Malam Farmer Group which are active farmer groups. Two active farmer groups each took 34 respondents consisting of 23 respondents from the Women's Farmer Group and 11 respondents from the Sedap Malam Farmer Group.

2.4. Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using qualitative descriptive analysis methods. To find out the second objective, namely knowing the percentage of farmer household decision making in preventing stunting, tabulation analysis was used.

Percentages are calculated by comparing who decides on each aspect of the activity with the total number of respondents. Data regarding decision making was analyzed into three variations of decision making patterns between husband and wife in the family used in this research, namely decision making as follows: (a) joint decision making, but the wife's influence is more dominant; (b)

joint decision making is equal, without anyone dominating; and (c) joint decision making, but the husband's influence is more dominant.

From the results of respondents' answers, the percentage will be calculated using the following formula:

$$P = (f / N) \times 100\%$$

Information: P = Percentage; f = frequency of each answer; and N = number of questionnaires.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Research Results

3.1.1. General Condition of Research Location

Based on the Lempake Village monograph in 2022, Lempake Village, North Samarinda District has an area of 34,501,700 m². The population in Lempake Village in 2022 will be 21,068 people, consisting of 10,837 men and 10,231 women; with 5,762 heads of families. The livelihoods of the people of Lempake Village are very diverse, consisting of farmers, civil servants, fishermen, farm workers, private employees, traders, others.

3.1.2. General Description of Farmer Household Decision Making in Stunting Prevention

Farming households, in carrying out their role as main supporters and initial pillars in preventing stunting, certainly have the right to make decisions in preventing stunting. One form of decision making in farming households is in terms of food provision. Farming household decision making in preventing stunting through food provision involves various factors that influence food selection and consumption. There are several influencing factors such as access to resources, knowledge and education, food consumption patterns, food availability and quality, food management and preparation, health conditions and access to health services, cultural influences and social norms and the availability of empowerment and education programs.

The majority of farming households in Lempake Village already have knowledge about stunting, so preventing stunting is one of the considerations in making decisions regarding household decision making. In Lempake Village they are also quite good at action or managing food supply, this is proven by the existence of farmers grow vegetables and fruit in their own gardens. The human resources in Lempake Village are on average quite effective in carrying out their farming business so that the farming activities carried out are quite productive for farmers. In Lempake Village they are also quite good at managing existing farmer groups, this is proven by the existence of regular meetings held by farmer groups. However, there are several obstacles, namely that there are still those who have limited knowledge regarding stunting and in decision making there is a lack of husband's role.

3.1.3. Respondent Characteristics

a. Age

Age level is one of the productive factors of a farmer in carrying out his farming business. Productive age is the age at which a person can work well to produce products and services. Based on Table 1, it can be seen that the ages of the farmer group members in Lempake Village who were used as respondents were mostly 16-56 years old with a percentage of 94.11% and those aged more than 56 years were 5.88%.

Table 1. Average age of respondents in Lempake Village

No	Age (Year)	Amount of People	Percentage (%)
1	0-15	0	0,00
2	16-56	32	94,11
3	>56	2	5,88

Total	34	100,00
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Source: Primary Data (processed), 2024

b. Level of education

Education level can play an important role in farmer household decision making regarding stunting prevention. Education level tends to be associated with knowledge about nutrition and health. The level of education is one of the factors that influences the way farmers make decisions, with education farmers' knowledge and access to information related to stunting can be higher and enable them to be better able to understand the importance of proper nutrition in preventing stunting and make better decisions related to this. . Knowledge about agriculture and stunting is not only formal education, but can also be obtained through non-formal education.

Lempake Village has several facilities that support educational aspects, such as school buildings. The farmer group that was used as respondents in terms of education was most dominant at the junior high school (SMP) level with a percentage of 38.23% with a total of 13 respondents and the lowest was at the Bachelor level with a percentage of 2.94% with a total of 1 respondent. . Thus, it can be seen that the level of educational awareness is still lacking, this happened because the mindset of parents in the past was more concerned with helping with work at home or in the fields rather than having to go to study at school.

Table 2. Respondents' Education in Lempake Village

No	Degree of Education	Amount of People	Percentage (%)
1	No School	0	0,00
2	Elementary School	9	26,47
3	Junior High School	13	38,23
4	Senior High School	11	32,35
5	Bachelor	1	2,94
	Total	34	100,00

Source: Primary Data (processed), 2024

c. Land ownership status

Land ownership status can influence farmers' decisions in land management and also their access to resources needed for agriculture. Land ownership status can vary from one farmer to another. Own land means that the owner has full rights to the land, including the right to use, manage and benefit from the land according to their wishes. The owner also has the right to sell, give or bequeath the land to someone else. Borrowed land refers to land that is used by a person or group without having ownership rights to the land. Usually, borrowed land is rented or lent by the land owner to another party for use for a certain period of time and those who use the borrowed land must pay rent or provide compensation to the land owner according to a predetermined agreement. The land ownership status of respondents in Lempake Village is 100% (34 people) is their own land.

Table 3. Land Ownership Status

No	Land Ownership Status	Amount of People	Percentage (%)
1	Own Land	34	100,00
2	Borrowed Land	0	0,00
3	Total	34	100,00

Source: Primary Data (processed), 2024

d. Land ownership

Land area is a measure of the area of land owned or used for agricultural or farming activities. The larger the area of land owned or managed, generally the potential to produce more agricultural production. Farmers who are respondents in Lempake Village on average carry out their farming business on 0.5-1 ha of land with a percentage of 97.05% or 33 people and around 3% or 1 person carry out their farming business on less than a ha of land.

Table 4. Land Ownership

No	Land Ownership (hectare)	Amount of People	Percentage (%)
1	<0,5	1	3%
2	0,5-1	33	97,05%
3	Total	34	100,00

Source: Primary Data (processed), 2024

3.1.4. Farmer Household Decision Making

The pattern of decision making in the household is based on three variations, namely: (1) Joint decision making, but the wife's influence is more dominant. (2) Joint decision making is equal, without anyone dominating, (3) Joint decision making, but the husband's influence is more dominant.

a. Providing diverse food

Based on the research results in Appendix 7, it was found that there are interesting decision-making patterns in providing diverse food. The wife's role in decision making in farming households is quite dominant, with an average percentage of joint decision making but the wife's influence is more dominant at 53.91%. This shows the important role and significant influence of wives in making decisions regarding the provision of various foods. Apart from that, there is also a fairly high percentage of decisions taken equally by husband and wife, namely 66.28%. This shows the collaboration and active involvement of both husband and wife in making decisions regarding the provision of diverse food. However, the percentage of dominant decision making by husbands is very low, only 0.98%. This indicates the need for more attention in increasing the role and involvement of husbands in decision making regarding the provision of diverse food.

b. Providing nutritious food

Based on the research results in Appendix 8, it was found that the wife's role in decision making in decision making in providing nutritious food is quite dominant. The average dominant joint decision making by the wife is 37.60%, indicating that the wife has quite a big influence in decisions related to providing nutritious food. However, there is also a fairly high percentage of decisions taken equally by husband and wife, namely 61.12%. This shows that there is good collaboration between husband and wife in making decisions regarding the provision of nutritious food. On the other hand, the percentage of dominant joint decision making by husbands is very low, only 1.26%. The husband's role appears to be more significant in the decision-making aspect of consuming supplements or vitamins, although it remains a low percentage. This shows that the husband's role in making decisions regarding the provision of nutritious food still needs to be improved.

c. Providing balanced food

Based on the research results in Appendix 9, regarding the provision of balanced food, it shows that the wife's role in decision making tends to be dominant. The average dominant joint decision making by the wife is 42.32%, indicating that the wife has a significant influence in decision making regarding the provision of balanced food. On the other hand, the percentage of dominant joint decision making by husbands is very low, only 0.58%. The husband's role appears to be more significant in decision making regarding when to give food to children, although still in a lower percentage. However, there is also a fairly high percentage of decisions taken equally by husband and

wife, namely 57.05%. This shows that both husband and wife play a role in making decisions regarding the provision of balanced food.

d. Providing safe food

Based on the research results in Appendix 10 regarding the provision of safe food, it shows that the wife's role in decision making is very dominant. The average dominant joint decision making by the wife is 59.23%, indicating that the wife has a large influence in decision making regarding the provision of safe food. On the other hand, the percentage of dominant joint decision making by husbands is quite low, only 3.78%. This shows that the husband's role in making decisions regarding the provision of safe food still needs to be improved. However, there is also a quite significant percentage of decisions taken equally by husband and wife, namely 36.97%. This shows that there is a good role between husband and wife in several aspects of decision making regarding the provision of safe food.

3.1.5 Comparison of Wife's Decision and Husband's Decision

In the household, there are often differences in decision making between husband and wife. This can be caused by differences in knowledge, experience and social roles between husband and wife in the household. Wives often have greater knowledge about food preparation because they are more involved in buying, cooking, and managing food in the household. Apart from that, factors such as education, experience and traditional roles in the household can also influence the wife's role in making decisions regarding food provision. On the other hand, husbands also have an important role in making decisions regarding food provision. Although in some cases husbands may be less involved in daily activities related to food, husbands' decisions can also influence the availability, accessibility and safety of food in the household.

The results of the field research showed that of the 34 respondents there were 23 wife respondents who were members of the female farmer group, on average the wife chose the dominant joint decision making pattern with a percentage of 48.30%, joint decision making was equivalent to 50.33% and joint decision making was dominant. husband has 1.35%. There were 11 husband respondents who were members of the farmer group, where the average decision making for the dominant joint decision making pattern with the wife was 53.70%, equal joint decision making was 44% and the husband's dominant joint decision making pattern was 2.27%.

Based on the results of field research, it appears that in groups of women farmers, equal joint decision making is higher compared to other types of decision making. This shows that in decision making by groups of women farmers, important decisions regarding agriculture and preventing stunting are taken jointly between husband and wife without the dominance of one party. This joint and equal decision making shows that there is healthy collaboration between husband and wife in terms of agricultural management and fulfilling family nutrition. Husband and wife work together to reach agreement on plant selection, agricultural techniques, processing of agricultural products, and prevention of stunting. This shows that in the group of women farmers, the roles of husband and wife are considered equally important in making decisions related to agriculture and family nutritional health. Good collaboration between husband and wife in making decisions can have a positive impact on stunting prevention, because decisions taken together tend to be more holistic and sustainable. On the other hand, in the group of husbands who are members of the farmer group, the wife still dominates joint decision making in a high percentage. Dominant joint decision-making by wives in farmer-husband groups can be caused by various factors, such as the wife's wider knowledge and experience the wife being usually actively involved in providing food, or the existence of an agreement between the husband and wife to give more decision-making power to the wife in matters this.

Table 9. Comparison of Wife's Decision and Husband's Decision

No	Food Supply Indicators	Farming Women's Group						Farmers Group					
		BD I	%	B S	%	BD S	%	BD I	%	BS	%	BD S	%
1	Providing Diverse Food	126	60,8	7	37,3	3	1,4	53	53,5	46	46,4	0	0,00
			6	8	68		4		3		6		
2	Providing Nutritious Food	147	45,6	1	53,7	2	0,6	44	28,5	106	68,8	4	2,59
			5	73	3		2		7		3		
3	Providing Balanced Food	34	29,5	8	69,5	1	0,8	38	69,0	17	30,9	0	0
			6	0	6		6		9				
4	Providing Safe Food	92	57,1	6	40,3	4	2,4	49	63,6	23	29,8	5	6,49
			4	5	7		8		3		7		
	Total	399	193,21	3	201,96	10	5,4	184	214,82	192	176,06	9	9,08
	Average	99,75	48,30	9	50,33	2,5	1,35	46	53,70	48	44	2,25	2,27

Source: Primary Data (processed), 2024

Description: The Women Farmers Group consists of 23 people; The Farmer Group consists of 11 people

Information : KWT: 23 people; KT: 11 people,

Decision-Making Patterns: BDI: Together with Dominant Wife, BS = Together as husband and wife, BDS = Together with Dominant Husband

3.2. Discussion

3.2.1. Identification of Farmer Household Decision-Making Processes in Stunting Prevention

Stunting prevention in Lempake Village, North Samarinda District, requires an in-depth understanding of the decision-making process in farming households. The research results show that the majority of decision making is carried out together as equals, where husband and wife have an equal role in this process. This shows high awareness of the importance of collaboration in overcoming children's health problems. The decision-making process begins with identifying the stunting problem and gathering information about stunting prevention. Husband and wife then choose alternative actions, evaluate alternatives, and finally make a decision together. These steps reflect awareness of the importance of accurate information and adequate knowledge in quality decision making. Several studies conducted in sub-Saharan African countries link women's decision-making power with the nutritional status of children [7].

Factors such as education, knowledge, and social support also influence the decision-making process. Increasing access to information and health services, as well as increasing the role of husbands in the decision-making process, can strengthen stunting prevention efforts in Lempake Village. Thus, balanced collaboration between husband and wife in making decisions regarding stunting prevention is very important to achieve optimal results. Increasing understanding of this process can be the basis for developing more effective stunting prevention programs in the future.

3.2.2. Farmer Household Decision-Making in Stunting Prevention

Stunting prevention is an important aspect in agriculture, especially for farming households which have a big role in providing food for the family and community. Farming households' decision-making in preventing stunting greatly influences children's health and quality of life. Decision making is divided into three variations, namely wife-dominant joint decision-making, equal joint decision-

making and husband-dominant joint decision-making. This is also in line with [8] regarding the influence of household decision making which influences stunting in children. Gender refers to the roles, attributes, behaviors, and opportunities associated with being male, female, or gender non-binary. Men and women display distinct health behaviors, encounter diverse health vulnerabilities, and receive varying responses from health systems. Currently, the prevalence of stunting in Rwanda is 33%. Despite the Rwanda government's extensive efforts to address stunting and promote gender equality in the country, no study has been conducted to examine the gender-related factors linked to stunting in Rwanda.

The results of research conducted by researchers in the field on 34 respondents showed that the majority of decisions were taken together as equals without anyone dominating. This indicates that there is balanced collaboration between husband and wife in making decisions regarding food, nutrition and family health. In this context, decisions taken are based on mutual agreement and considerations involving both parties, without any party having full control over decision making. This balanced collaboration can be considered a positive factor in stunting prevention efforts, because it allows for a better understanding of family needs and more effective prevention strategies.

a. Providing various foods

Diverse food refers to the concept of consuming a variety of foods, both in terms of nutritional sources and the types of food consumed. Consuming a variety of foods is very important because each type of food contains different nutrients, and only by consuming various types of food can we ensure adequate nutrition needed by the body. During the period of growth and development, food diversity is very important to ensure that children get sufficient nutrition to optimize their growth and development. [9] stated that the problem of stunting is influenced by low access to food in terms of quantity and nutritional quality, and is often not diverse. Balanced nutrition needs to be introduced and accustomed to in everyday life. For children during their growth period, increasing protein sources is highly recommended in a higher proportion than carbohydrates, as well as continuing to get used to consuming fruit and vegetables.

The research results show that the majority of decisions made for various food supply activities are decided together as equals. If decisions regarding various foods are decided equally by husband and wife, this shows that there is good collaboration between the two in terms of selecting and processing various foods. This joint and equal decision can have a positive impact in preventing stunting because the various types of food consumed can meet various nutritional needs. In the context of farming households in Lempake Village, this joint and equal decision is achieved through dialogue and discussion between husband and wife regarding the choice of food to be purchased or processed. Husband and wife can share knowledge and experience with each other to ensure that the family gets a balanced and sufficient nutritional intake.

It is important to continue to encourage healthy collaboration between husband and wife in making decisions regarding diverse foods. This can be done through education about the importance of diverse food for family health, as well as creating awareness of the active role of both parties in achieving this goal. Success in making equal joint decisions regarding diverse foods can also be an example for other households around them, resulting in increased awareness of the importance of consuming nutritious and diverse foods to prevent stunting. The majority of Lempake Village farmers have knowledge regarding the provision of various types of food. Knowledge about food provision for various respondents is followed by the action of planting food crops to ensure a variety of food in the family and consuming harvests according to needs. This knowledge regarding diverse foods does not specifically come from a particular organization, but is based on the respondents' own desire for food diversity.

b. Providing nutritious food

Diverse foods refer to foods that contain various types of nutrients needed by the body to maintain optimal health and body function. Diverse foods contain various kinds of vitamins, minerals, proteins, fats, carbohydrates, fiber and other substances needed by the body for healthy growth and development. Consuming a variety of foods is very important to meet the daily nutritional needs needed by the body to stay healthy and energetic. The importance of a diverse diet lies primarily in its ability to provide the nutrients the body needs.[9] stated that balanced nutrition needs to be introduced and accustomed to in everyday life. For children during their growth period, increasing protein sources is highly recommended in a higher proportion than carbohydrates, as well as continuing to get used to consuming fruit and vegetables. Furthermore, it was stated [10] that fulfilling nutrition, especially in the first 1,000 days of life, is the first effort to avoid stunting. Fulfillment of nutrition includes nutrition during pregnancy and childhood up to the age of two years.

The research results show that the majority of decision making for nutritious food provision activities are decided together as equals. This shows that husband and wife ensure that the family gets adequate and balanced nutritional intake. This joint and equal decision is important in efforts to prevent stunting because adequate and balanced nutrition is very necessary for the growth and development of children. It is very important to continue to encourage healthy collaboration between husband and wife in making decisions regarding nutritious food. This can be done through counseling and education about the importance of balanced nutrition for family health, as well as creating awareness of the active role of both parties in achieving this goal.

Success in making equal joint decisions regarding nutritious food can also help reduce the risk of malnutrition and stunting among children. Thus, collaboration between husband and wife in this matter can have a big positive impact on the health and development of children and the entire family. In the context of farming households in Lempake Subdistrict, this joint and equal decision may involve discussions between husband and wife about the type of food to be purchased or processed, as well as cooking methods that maintain its nutritional content. Husbands and wives can support each other in choosing foods that contain important nutrients such as protein, iron, calcium and vitamins. The majority of Lempake Village farmers have knowledge regarding the provision of nutritious food. Knowledge of nutritious food can be seen from planting activities that ensure nutritional variations in preventing stunting, such as vegetables and fruit, as well as information regarding nutritious food obtained through health organizations.

c. Providing balanced food

Balanced food is food that contains various nutrients needed by the body in the right amounts. A balanced diet must provide energy, protein, fat, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals in proportions that suit the body's needs for growth, development and maintaining health. The importance of a balanced diet lies in its ability to provide sufficient nutrition for the body to carry out its functions optimally. A balanced diet is also important to support children's growth and development and maintain health at all stages of life.

The results of the research show that the majority of decision making for balanced food provision activities are decided together as equals, joint decisions between husband and wife in making decisions about nutritious food are very important. The decision-making of husbands and wives in farming households in Lempake Village regarding balanced food shows healthy and harmonious collaboration within the family to maintain a balanced and nutritious diet. This joint decision reflects agreement and good communication between the two in choosing healthy and nutritious food for the family

In the context of farming households in Lempake Village, joint and equal decisions regarding balanced food can mean that husband and wife both understand the importance of consuming food that contains balanced nutrition, including protein, carbohydrates, fats, vitamins and minerals. Both parties may remind and support each other in choosing food that suits the family's nutritional needs.

According to the knowledge of farmers in Lempake Village, the majority do not know about providing balanced food. The lack of knowledge about balanced food is due to a lack of access to information related to balanced food, where the provision of balanced food is still less familiar among the public. This lack of knowledge can be seen from the absence of certain consumption patterns that are in accordance with the nutrients needed by the body.

d. Providing safe food

Safe food is food that is free from microbial contamination, dangerous chemicals and other substances that can harm human health if consumed. Safe food is very important to maintain human health and prevent disease caused by microbial contamination or dangerous chemicals in food. Consuming safe food is also important to support healthy growth and development, especially in children. [11] stated that one of the important interventions to prevent stunting is to ensure food safety so that the food consumed is safe and of good quality.

The research results show that the majority of decision making for activities providing safe food is decided jointly by the wife, this is because the wife is often responsible for choosing and buying food for the family. The wife's role in choosing safe food can help prevent the risk of food poisoning and food-related health problems and the wife is also often responsible for storing and processing food in the household. A wife's knowledge about how to store and process food properly can help maintain food safety in the household. In terms of knowledge, farmers in Lempake Village have knowledge regarding the provision of safe food. Knowledge of safe food can be seen from the actions of separating cooked and raw food, washing eating utensils, and washing vegetables and fruit.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the research and discussion, several conclusions were drawn, namely:

1. The decision-making process begins with identifying the stunting problem and gathering information about stunting prevention. The husband and wife then jointly choose alternative actions, evaluate these alternatives, and finally make a decision together. This reflects high awareness of the importance of having accurate information and adequate knowledge in making quality decisions.
2. Decision making by farmer households in preventing stunting in Lempake Village shows that the role of wives in making decisions regarding food is very dominant in farmer households. However, the husband's role is also involved, although to a lesser extent.

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